

www.bjisrd.com

**ORGANIZATION OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES IN
ACCORDANCE WITH INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS**

Akhmedova Mavluda

Associate Professor of the department of Management, International School of Finance
Technology and Science (ISFT institute), Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of improving corporate governance in joint-stock companies. The effectiveness of the corporate governance system is highlighted in protecting the rights and interests of shareholders, as well as in improving the financial performance of the company. Reforms aimed at developing corporate governance practices in the Republic of Uzbekistan, international experiences and modern management principles are analyzed. The article also develops recommendations on making the management system more transparent, strengthening cooperation between shareholders and supervisory boards, and increasing the efficiency of corporate governance through the use of digital technologies. The results of the study are of scientific and practical importance for developing strategic management in joint-stock companies and ensuring economic efficiency.

Keywords corporate governance, joint-stock company, international standards, corporate transparency, financial transparency, strategic management, supervisory board, shareholder rights, digital technologies, corporate culture, international experience, regulatory and legal documents, corporate governance code, expert assessment, rating methods, dynamic analysis, comparative analysis, investment attraction, enterprise efficiency.

Introduction

In the process of development and modernization of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, improving the corporate governance system is recognized as one of the priority areas. This process involves increasing the efficiency of joint-stock companies, introducing management principles in line with international standards, and strengthening investor confidence. In this regard, a number of important decisions and decrees adopted by the head of our state serve as an important factor in further improving the corporate governance system.

In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. PF-5718 dated April 24, 2019 "On measures to further improve the corporate governance system in joint-stock companies" is aimed at introducing a management system based on international standards in joint-stock companies and increasing financial transparency. Also, the Resolution No. PQ-4954 dated January 14, 2021 "On measures to introduce modern digital technologies in managing the activities of enterprises" ensured the acceleration of the use of modern technologies in the corporate governance system.

These documents serve to strengthen the legal and organizational foundations of the corporate governance system, increase the effectiveness of strategic management in joint-stock companies. Therefore, the issues of improving governance in joint-stock companies are of urgent importance not only theoretically, but also practically. This article analyzes the current issues of corporate governance, its international experience, as well as the prospects for its development in Uzbekistan.

Literature review

A number of foreign and domestic economists and researchers (B. Tricker, G. Means, M. Becht, R. Morck, I. Ansof, S. Meloun, S. Kukura, J. Johnson, K. Scholes and R. Whittington, L. Putterman and H. Dong, K. Naqvi and E. Ginting, F. Nita, S. Teguh, A. Adeemi and B. Akkers, Papenfub, A. Dementeva, B. Berkinov, R. Yaushev, I. Butikov, Z. Ashurov, M. Vokhidov, Sh. Zaynutdinov, M. Khamidullin, D. Suyunov, A. Khoshimov, M. Khudaykulov, M. Tashkhodjayev, G. Khangeldiyeva, D. Begmatova, A. Khashimov and a number of other scientists) have conducted research on corporate governance and its improvement.

Research methodology

The article uses modern management approaches to study the issues of organizing corporate governance in joint-stock companies in accordance with international standards. The research widely uses scientific and methodological methods such as observation, comparison, systematic and comprehensive approach, experiment, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, classification, economic and statistical analysis, comparative and dynamic analysis, rating, as well as expert assessment. These approaches provide important practical and theoretical foundations for improving the efficiency of the corporate governance system, studying international experience and adapting it to local conditions.

Analysis and discussion of results

Relations in all sectors of the economy must be ensured, first of all, in a normative and legal manner. According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "the state and its bodies, other organizations, officials, civil society institutions and citizens shall act in accordance with the Constitution and laws ¹. "

As in other sectors, Uzbekistan has adopted a number of regulatory and other regulatory documents on the organization and improvement of corporate governance in joint-stock companies with a state share.

When organizing corporate governance, it is advisable to study documents in two directions. The first is regulatory and legal documents and the second is regulatory documents. A regulatory and legal document is understood as " an official document adopted in accordance with the legislation, aimed at establishing, amending or repealing legal norms as generally binding state instructions." As a regulatory

¹ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Article 15// www.lex.uz

document, our work ²will consider the Corporate Governance Code ³and the Corporate Governance Rules for Enterprises with State Participation .⁴

Based on the analysis of regulatory legal acts in the field of corporate governance in the dissertation, a list of 41 current regulatory legal acts is presented in Appendix 4 and Figure 1

Figure 1. Regulatory and legal documents regulating the activities of joint-stock companies of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁵

The main document regulating the activities of joint-stock companies with a state share is the Law "On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders' Rights". This Law, adopted in a new edition in 2014, consists of 13 chapters and 116 articles.

This Law regulates relations in the field of the establishment, operation, reorganization and liquidation of joint-stock companies, as well as the protection of shareholders' rights.

First, if we turn to the concept of joint-stock companies with a state share, the Regulation on the Procedure for Managing State Share Packages (Shares) in the Authorized Capital of Economic Companies, registered with the Ministry of Justice on April 27, 2005 under No. 1473, defines a state share as a state share package (share) in the authorized capital of economic companies issued on behalf of the state by the State Committee for Privatization, Demonopoly and Competition Development or the State Assets Management Center. However, other ministries and departments that own share packages, including local government bodies, state unitary enterprises and state institutions, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Fund for Reconstruction and Development, are not included.

² Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan " On Regulatory and Legal Acts " /www.lex.uz/

³Approved by the resolution of the Commission for Improving the Efficiency of Joint Stock Companies and Improving the Corporate Governance System No. 02-02/1-187 dated 11.02.2016

⁴Approved by the resolution of the Commission for Improving the Efficiency of Joint-Stock Companies and Improving the Corporate Governance System No. 24/1-989 dated 27.04.2018

⁵ Developed by the author

Since, in accordance with Articles 178-179 of the Civil Code, property attached to state unitary enterprises and institutions belongs to them on the basis of the right of operational management, its owner is the state.

Given that the Central Bank and the Fund for Reconstruction and Development are also fully state-owned institutions, it is appropriate that their share packages also be designated as state shares.

The state share was clearly and completely transferred to existing joint-stock companies in 2016, according to which, "shares owned by state administration bodies, local government bodies, state unitary enterprises and state institutions, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the Fund for Reconstruction and Development are considered state shares in the authorized capital of joint-stock companies ⁶. "

Two conceptual documents have been adopted on ⁷the introduction and improvement of corporate governance in state-owned enterprises . In particular, the first document includes ⁸:

The organizational structure of 623 joint-stock companies operating in the republic has been revised;

The word "state" was removed from the names of 17 joint-stock companies, meaning that all organizations previously called state joint-stock companies were renamed joint-stock companies;

A provision on the selection of directors, in which foreign managers can participate, was included in the charters of joint-stock companies;

Based on the experience of Germany and other developed countries, the Corporate Governance Code was approved;

721 heads of 371 joint-stock companies were certified. Of these, 350 (49%) passed the certification, 228 (31%) passed the certification conditionally, and 143 (20%) were found unfit for their positions;

In order to train and educate modern managers, the Corporate Governance Research and Education Center was established on the basis of the Higher Business School (30.09.2015, PQ-2414). Together with the European School of Management and Technology (Germany), 160 managers were trained, and 80 of them gained experience in large German companies.

Requirements for assessing the effectiveness of the executive body in enterprises with a state share were approved ⁹;

A "Single Internet Portal of Corporate Information" was created;

The practice of appointing state representatives and supervisory boards of state-owned companies from among individuals with a corporate governance qualification certificate has been introduced.

In addition, the second document ¹⁰approved the Strategy for Reforming State-Owned Enterprises, within the framework of which it is established to implement the following:

Development of draft laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Property Management" and "On Privatization"; Establishing criteria for ownership of enterprises with state participation (natural monopoly, operating in the field of strategic interest, etc.), and annually introducing a new practice based on these criteria, the "sell or explain" principle, that is, if the need to keep a particular enterprise in the state is not justified, it will be forced to sell;

⁶Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 17, 2016 No. PQ - 2635 " On measures to further improve corporate governance in joint-stock companies with a predominant state share "

⁷ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 24, 2015 " On measures to introduce modern corporate governance methods in joint-stock companies " No. PF - 4720 // www.lex.uz

⁸ Formed based on information from the State Assets Management Agency

⁹Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 207 dated 28.07.2015 "On the introduction of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of joint-stock companies and other business entities with state shares" //lex.uz

¹⁰Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 166 dated March 29, 2021 "On approval of the Strategy for the management and reform of state-owned enterprises for 2021-2025" //lex.uz

determining commercial and non-commercial goals for enterprises with state participation, creating equal conditions for enterprises with state participation and non-state legal entities, including the transformation of all state unitary enterprises into business companies, and the separation of the state's ownership (shareholder, participant, founder) and regulatory functions;

gradual election of members of management bodies on a competitive basis, the involvement of independent members in the supervisory board, the establishment of committees under it, and the termination of the activities of audit commissions;

introducing the practice of hearing information on the effectiveness of enterprises' activities and the implementation of the Strategy in the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, creating a website for enterprises, etc.;

Independent election (appointment) of members of the executive body and supervisory board of enterprises with state participation by them based on the principles of corporate governance (decisions of the general meeting of shareholders, supervisory board and founders);

Establishing a supervisory board, internal audit service, and audit committee within the supervisory board at state-owned enterprises;

Establish a "compliance system" (compliance) service in joint-stock companies whose shares are listed on the stock exchange and whose state share is more than 50 percent;

to prepare a summary report on the results of the activities of state-owned enterprises and, starting in 2022, to post it annually on the official website of the State Assets Management Agency;

Extending the terms of office of members of the executive body and supervisory board from one to three years and abolishing the state's special right to "golden shares".

As a result of implementing this Strategy:

Gradually increase the share of independent members in the supervisory boards of state-owned enterprises to 30 percent;

reduce the number of state-owned enterprises by 75 percent;

It is envisaged that there will be primary and secondary public placements of shares of enterprises with the participation of 20 countries.

In general, the analysis of regulatory legal acts showed that additional requirements for joint-stock companies with a state share are established by a number of regulatory legal acts. In particular, 18 requirements for joint-stock companies and an additional 16 requirements for joint-stock companies with a state share are established, such as the registration of companies, the formation of management bodies, ensuring transparency, and the formation of supervisory bodies.

Conclusion

The results of this study showed that aligning the corporate governance system in joint-stock companies with international standards is important for increasing economic efficiency and strengthening investor confidence. Modern principles of corporate governance, including transparency, accountability, and effective communication with stakeholders, are recognized as key factors in ensuring the sustainable development of joint-stock companies.

Proposals were developed to improve the management system, widely introduce digital technologies, and strengthen cooperation between management bodies and shareholders by studying international experience and adapting it to local conditions.

The modern scientific methods used in the study, including comparative analysis, economic-statistical analysis, and expert assessment, made it possible to conduct an in-depth study of the corporate governance system in joint-stock companies, identify existing problems, and develop practical recommendations for their elimination.

The following are recommended for the future development of corporate governance:

1. Strengthening the legal and institutional framework for the full implementation of international governance standards.
2. Optimization of the control system through the widespread use of digital control technologies.
3. Further improve mechanisms aimed at protecting the rights and interests of shareholders.
4. Strengthening the principles of social responsibility of corporate governance and increasing its impact on financial stability.

The results of this study serve as a practical and theoretical basis for the formation of a corporate governance system in joint-stock companies that meets international standards.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev No. PF-5718 dated April 24, 2019 "On measures to further improve the corporate governance system in joint-stock companies."
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Resolution No. PQ-4954 dated January 14, 2021 "On measures to introduce modern digital technologies in the management of enterprise activities."
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders' Rights" (2014, new edition).
4. "Corporate Governance Code". Republic of Uzbekistan, 2015.
5. OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development). "G20/OECD Principles of Corporate Governance." OECD Publishing, Paris, 2015.
6. Tricker, RI "Corporate Governance: Principles, Policies, and Practices." Oxford University Press, 2019.
7. Ansoff, I. "Strategic Management." Palgrave Macmillan, 2007.
8. Means, G., & Berle, A. "The Modern Corporation and Private Property." Transaction Publishers, 1991.
9. Naqvi, K., & Ginting, E. "Improving Corporate Governance in Emerging Markets." Asian Development Bank Institute, 2020.
10. Regulation "On the Procedure for Implementing Activities on the Management of State Share Packages in the Authorized Fund of Economic Companies" (April 27, 2005, Ministry of Justice List: No. 1473).
11. Papenfub, A. "Transparency in Corporate Governance: A Quantitative Analysis." Springer International Publishing, 2018.
12. Begmatova, D., & Tashkhodjayev, M. "Development of the Management System in Joint-Stock Companies in Uzbekistan." Tashkent: Institute of Economics and Innovation, 2022.

13. Berkinov, B., & Yaushev, R. "Problems of improving governance in enterprises with state shares." Scientific journal "Economics and Management", 2020.
14. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. "Corporate Governance Principles for Banks." Bank for International Settlements, 2015.
15. "Strategy for Reforming State-Owned Enterprises" State Assets Management Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2021.
16. Kuznetsov, P., & Dong, H. "Corporate Governance in Transition Economies: A Comparative Perspective." Cambridge University Press, 2016.
17. "Single Internet Portal of Corporate Information" (www.openinfo.uz).